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Abstract

Based on the finite element method, a model of geometrically nonlinear deformation of bar elements is developed. Using the implicit Ritz method, a nonlinear system of algebraic equations is obtained to determine unknown nodal displacements and stresses in finite elements. The system is solved iteratively by the Newton–Raphson method. An algorithm and a computer program for numerical investigation of the problem have been developed. Test examples are presented.

Keywords: finite element, stress, strain, bar element, stiffness matrix, direction cosines, coordinate system, displacements.

Introduction

This work represents one of the directions of theoretical studies of the static behavior of three-dimensional bar structures. Within the framework of these studies, in the work of Nigmatov M.Zh. [1], displacements of the platform support points on the soil foundation were determined. However, these studies cannot be considered sufficient for analyzing the stress–strain state, strength, and stability of an offshore platform.

It is necessary to determine displacements of the entire bar system constituting the platform, then proceed to strains and stresses (as well as axial and shear forces and bending moments). Most importantly, when considering a bar mechanical system, the possibility of large displacements, i.e., geometric nonlinearity, is often neglected.

Therefore, a reliable assessment of the elastic behavior of the “bar offshore platform–seabed foundation” system is possible only if geometric nonlinearity of the bar component is taken into account. In this regard, there arises a need to develop theoretical and methodological approaches for comprehensive investigation of the static and dynamic behavior of spatial bar platforms resting on inclined layered foundations under the action of constant and variable external forces.

Problem Statement

The aim of this work is to investigate the static elastic stress–strain state of spatial bar elements under various environmental loads.

To achieve this objective, the following tasks are solved:

- numerical solution of statics problems for the “platform–foundation” mechanical system considering possible large displacements of the platform bar structure using two-node finite elements;
- numerical solution of dynamics problems for the “platform–foundation” mechanical system considering possible large displacements of the platform bar structure under wave loading conditions.

Method and Solution Formulation

Obtaining analytical solutions in geometrically and physically nonlinear problems is a complex mathematical issue and is possible only in special cases. Therefore, modern numerical methods using computers are employed for solving such problems.

Currently, the finite element method (FEM) has become widely used for studying the stress–strain state of complex structures.

The main difficulty in solving nonlinear problems by FEM lies in constructing the tangent stiffness matrix, which depends on displacements. Depending on the principles used to formulate equilibrium equations, different forms of tangent stiffness matrices are obtained.

In [2], the basic relations are derived from the principle of virtual displacements. In [3], the more general Hamilton–Ostrogradsky principle is used, while [4] directly applies Lagrange equations.

One of the most common structural systems is bar systems. Recently, interest in such systems has increased not only for analyzing purely bar structures, but also due to their applicability in modeling continua and solid bodies through idealized bar models.

Discrete bar models allow the behavior of plates, shells, and solid bodies to be described.

A reliable estimation of deformations in such systems is possible only when nonlinearity is taken into account.

Numerical Method and Solution Procedure

The fundamental equations of nonlinear elasticity are solved approximately by transforming them into algebraic form through mathematical and physical discretization methods.

The finite element method was first applied to continuum mechanics problems in the mid-1950s and has since become an exceptionally effective tool. Although FEM is used for solving problems similar to those addressed by the finite difference method, they are based on different principles. In the finite difference method, derivatives in differential equations are approximated by difference relations. The mathematical basis of FEM is the calculus of variations.

The differential equation describing the problem together with the boundary conditions is used to formulate a variational problem, which is then solved directly. From this point of view, FEM can be regarded as an implicit application of the Ritz method over separate subdomains. In FEM, the physical problem is replaced by a piecewise-smooth model.

The main stages of FEM in displacement formulation are as follows:

1. Definition of initial data, including:
 - coordinates of nodal points in the global coordinate system;
 - mutual arrangement of finite elements;
 - geometric and stiffness parameters of each structural element.
2. Determination of nodal locations of elements in the local coordinate system (LCS).
3. Construction of the element stiffness matrix in the LCS.
4. Calculation of direction cosines for each element and transformation matrices from local to global coordinate systems (GCS).
5. Assembly of the global stiffness matrix for the entire structure.
6. Imposition of constraints eliminating rigid-body motions.
7. Calculation of resultant nodal forces at each node.
8. Determination of nodal displacements and stress state of finite elements.

Methods developed for linear systems can also be applied when geometric nonlinearity is considered. Accounting for nonlinearity leads to a governing system containing nonlinear terms with respect to the unknowns. Since closed-form solutions cannot generally be obtained, iterative approximation procedures must be used.

Geometric nonlinearity causes the relationship between the strain vector and displacement vector to become nonlinear.

In FEM, nonlinear problems are formulated as a system of nonlinear algebraic equations:

$$[K(U)]\{U\} = \{Q\}, \quad (1)$$

where:

$\{U\}$ - unknown displacements, $\{Q\}$ - generalized external nodal loads. The problem consists in determining the unknown parameters $\{U\}$ as functions of the external actions $\{Q\}$.

The governing equations for a finite element are derived using the principle of virtual displacements.

The strain vector is represented as:

$$\{\varepsilon\} = \{\varepsilon_0\} + \{\varepsilon_L\}, \quad \{\varepsilon_0\} = [B_0]\{\delta\}, \quad \{\varepsilon_L\} = [B_L]\{\delta\}, \quad [\bar{B}] = [B_0] + [B_L] \quad (2)$$

where:

$[B_0]$ - linear, $[B_L]$ - nonlinear strain component, $\{\delta\}$ - nodal displacement matrix. The relationship between the

stress vector σ and the strain vector ε is given by $\{\sigma\} = [D]\{\varepsilon\}$,

where $[D]$ - is the elasticity matrix.

The equilibrium equations are expressed as:

$$\int_V d\{\varepsilon\}^T \{\sigma\} dV - d\{\delta\}^T \{Q\} = 0,$$

where $\{Q\}$ -is the residual force vector.

Using the relations $d\{\varepsilon\} = [\bar{B}]d\{\delta\}$, taking into account $d\{\delta\} \neq 0$, the equilibrium equations are obtained

$$\{\psi\} = \int_V [\bar{B}]^T \{\sigma\} dV - \{Q\} = 0 \quad (3)$$

where $\{\psi\}$ - the unbalanced force residual represents the sum of the external and internal forces of the element.

By varying the equilibrium equations (3) with respect to the displacements $d\{\delta\}$ taking into account

$$d\{Q\} = 0 \text{ one obtains: } d\{\psi\} = \int_V d[\bar{B}]^T \{\sigma\} dV + \int_V [\bar{B}]^T d\{\sigma\} dV. \text{ Since}$$

$$d\{\varepsilon\} = [\bar{B}]d\{\delta\}, \quad d\{\sigma\} = [D]d\{\varepsilon\} = [D][\bar{B}]d\{\delta\}, \quad d[\bar{B}]^T = d([B_0]^T + [B_L]^T) = d[B_L]^T,$$

Then

$$d\{\psi\} = \int_V d[B_L]^T [\delta] dV + \int_V [\bar{K}] d\{\delta\} \quad (4)$$

Where $[\bar{K}] = \int_V [\bar{B}]^T [D][B] dV = [K_0] + [K_L]$, here $[K_0]$ and $[K_L]$ respectively, the element stiffness matrices

corresponding to small and finite displacements.

The expressions for evaluating these matrices are given by:

$$[K_0] = \int_V [B_0]^T [D][B_0] dV,$$

$$[K_L] = \int_V [B_0]^T [D][B_L] dV + \int_V [B_L]^T [D][B_L] dV + \int_V [B_L]^T [D][B_0] dV$$

$[K_L]$ - The large-displacement matrix accounts for the geometric nonlinearity of the problem.

The first term in Eq. (4) can be represented as follows:

$$\int_V d[B_L]^T \{\sigma\} dV = [K_\sigma] d\{\delta\} \quad (5)$$

Where $[K_\sigma]$ - a symmetric matrix depending on the stress magnitude — the initial stress matrix.

Then $d\{\psi\} = ([K_0] + [K_\sigma] + [K_L])d\{\delta\} = [K_T]d\{\delta\}$, where $[K_T]$ - complete tangent stiffness matrix

Given the stiffness matrices of the individual elements $[K_T]$, the global stiffness matrix of the system $[K_T^C]$ is assembled by summation over all elements: $[K_T^C] = \sum_{i=1}^m [K_T]_i$, where m - total number of elements.

Similarly assembled $\{\psi\}^C = \sum_{i=1}^m \{\psi\}_i$ и $\{u\} = \sum_{i=1}^m \{u\}_i$, где $\{u\}$ и $\{\psi\}^C$ - the displacement vector and the system residual force vector, respectively.

The governing nonlinear system of equations for the static finite element problem can be written as follows:

$$d\{\psi\}^C = [K_T^C] d\{u\} \quad (6)$$

Equation system (6) is solved by the iterative Newton–Raphson method, whose basic idea is as follows

$\{u\} = \{u\}_n$ - an initial approximation obtained from linear theory. To refine the obtained solution, the residual

force vector is expanded into a Taylor series:

$$\{\psi\{u\}_{n+1}\} = \{\psi\{u\}_n\} + \left(\frac{d\psi}{du}\right)_n \Delta\{u\}_n \quad (7)$$

The corrected solution must also satisfy the equilibrium conditions $\{\psi\{u\}_{n+1}\} = 0$, and the correction to the solution is determined by the formula $\Delta\{u\}_n = -[K_T^C]^{-1} \{\psi\}_n$,

Where $[K_T^C]$ - the tangent stiffness matrix determined for the displacements and strains corresponding to the approximate solution $\{u\}_n$.

Determination of the Direction Cosine Matrix. The beginning of the bar is denoted by index i , and the end by j . A global coordinate system (GCS) is introduced. In addition to the global coordinate system $oxyz$, a local coordinate system $O'/x'/y'/z'$ is introduced, where the O'/x' is aligned with the bar axis, while the O'/y' and O'/z' are directed along the principal axes of inertia of the cross-section.

Let the coordinates of the bar element end nodes be denoted as (x_i, y_i, z_i) and (x_j, y_j, z_j)

The transformation from the LCS to the GCS is performed using the direction cosine matrix:

$$L = \begin{bmatrix} L_0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & L_0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & L_0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & L_0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Where $L_0 = \begin{bmatrix} t_{11} & t_{21} & t_{31} \\ t_{12} & t_{22} & t_{32} \\ t_{13} & t_{23} & t_{33} \end{bmatrix}$ - orientation matrix of the LCS relative to the GCS.

Since the coordinate cosines of the bar element are known, the direction cosines of the xxx-axis can be determined from the following formulas: $t_{11} = \frac{x_j - x_i}{l}$, $t_{21} = \frac{y_j - y_i}{l}$, $t_{31} = \frac{z_j - z_i}{l}$, where

$$l_1 = \sqrt{(x_j - x_i)^2 + (y_j - y_i)^2 + (z_j - z_i)^2} \text{ - bar length}$$

To determine the remaining parameters, an auxiliary point $D(x,y,z)$ is chosen outside the element such that nodes i, j , and point D lie in a plane containing one of the principal axes of inertia of the element cross-section:

$$t_{12} = \frac{a_1}{\sqrt{a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2}}, t_{22} = \frac{a_2}{\sqrt{a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2}}, t_{32} = \frac{a_3}{\sqrt{a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2}}$$

Then

$$a_1 = t_2 t_{31} - t_3 t_{21}, \quad a_2 = t_3 t_{11} - t_1 t_{31}, \quad a_3 = t_1 t_{21} - t_2 t_{11}; \quad t_1 = \frac{x_D - x_i}{l_1}, \quad t_2 = \frac{y_D - y_i}{l_1}, \quad t_3 = \frac{z_D - z_i}{l_1};$$

$$l_1 = \sqrt{(x_D - x_i)^2 + (y_D - y_i)^2 + (z_D - z_i)^2} - \text{length of segment } iD.$$

The direction cosines of the third set are determined using the following formulas:

$$t_{13} = t_{21} t_{32} - t_{31} t_{22}, \quad t_{23} = t_{31} t_{12} - t_{11} t_{32}, \quad t_{33} = t_{11} t_{22} - t_{21} t_{12} \quad (9)$$

All these relations are derived from the orthogonality conditions of vectors directed along the coordinate axes.

One of the important stages of the finite element method is discretization and the choice of finite element type, since both the success of solving the problem as a whole and the accuracy of the solutions depend on these factors. Discretization of bar systems by rectangular finite elements and reduction of the problem to plane stress or plane strain analysis lead to significant discrepancies in both displacements and stresses compared with exact solutions. For large displacements, all strain components are of the same order. Therefore, in order to obtain a correct and convergent solution, all second-order strain terms must be taken into account. In this work, two types of finite elements are used for the analysis of finite displacements: a bar finite element with 12 degrees of freedom and a bar finite element with 6 degrees of freedom [4,13].

Bar Element with Six Degrees of Freedom.

The constitutive equations of a three-dimensional bar system in the local coordinate system (LCS) $Ox'/y'/z'$,

where the direction of the Ox' coincides with the bar axis, are given by:

$$\{\sigma\} = [D]\{\varepsilon\} \quad (10)$$

Where $\{\sigma\} = \{\sigma_x\}$, $\{\varepsilon\} = \{\varepsilon_x\}$, the strain vector is reduced to a single component

$$\varepsilon_x = \frac{du}{dx} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{du}{dx} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dv}{dx} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dx} \right)^2 \right] \quad (11)$$

Assume that the relationship between the components and the displacement parameters is given by

$$\{u\} = [N]\{\delta\} \quad (12)$$

Where $\{u\}^T = \{u \quad v \quad w\}$ - displacements of an arbitrary point of the bar

$\{\delta\}^T = \{u_i \quad v_i \quad w_i \quad u_j \quad v_j \quad w_j\}$ - nodal displacement matrix,

$$[N] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 - \zeta & \zeta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 - \zeta & \zeta & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 - \zeta & \zeta \end{bmatrix} \text{ shape function, where } \zeta = \frac{x}{l}$$

The strain matrix $\{\varepsilon\}$ is written in the form $\{\varepsilon\} = \{\varepsilon_0\} + \{\varepsilon_L\}$, where

$$\{\varepsilon_0\} = \left\{ \frac{du}{dx} \right\} = \frac{1}{l} [-1 \quad 1 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 0] \begin{Bmatrix} u_i \\ u_j \\ v_i \\ v_j \\ w_i \\ w_j \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{1}{l} \{u_j - u_i\} = [B_0]\{\delta\}.$$

Express $\left\{ \frac{dv}{dx} \right\}$ and $\left\{ \frac{dw}{dx} \right\}$ in terms of nodal displacements

$$\begin{aligned} \left\{ \frac{dv}{dx} \right\} &= \frac{1}{l} [0 \quad 0 \quad -1 \quad 1 \quad 0 \quad 0] \{\delta\} = \frac{1}{l} \{v_j - v_i\}, \\ \left\{ \frac{dw}{dx} \right\} &= \frac{1}{l} [0 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad -1 \quad 1] \{\delta\} = \frac{1}{l} \{w_j - w_i\} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Then $\{\varepsilon\} = [B_L]\{\delta\}$, $[B_L] = \left\{ \frac{du}{dx} \quad \frac{dv}{dx} \quad \frac{dw}{dx} \right\} \cdot \frac{1}{l} \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} =$
 $= \frac{1}{2l} \{-(u_j - u_i), (u_j - u_i), -(v_j - v_i), (v_j - v_i), -(w_j - w_i), (w_j - w_i)\}.$

The bar element stiffness matrix $[K_0]$ is given by

$$[K_0] = \frac{EF}{l} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

where E and F are the modulus of elasticity and the cross-sectional area of the bar, respectively, and l is the bar length.

The initial stress matrix is calculated using the following formula:

$$[K_\sigma] = \int_V [G]^T [S] dV \quad (16)$$

Where

$$[G] = \frac{1}{l} \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, [S] = [S_0] + [S_L], [S_0] = E \begin{bmatrix} \frac{du}{dx} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{du}{dx} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{du}{dx} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$[S_L] = \frac{E}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \left(\frac{du}{dx}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{dv}{dx}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dx}\right)^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \left(\frac{du}{dx}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{dv}{dx}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dx}\right)^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \left(\frac{du}{dx}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{dv}{dx}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dx}\right)^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Thus, the final form of the initial stress matrix is

$$[K_\sigma] = EF(\varepsilon_0 + \varepsilon_L) \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

Bar Element with Twelve Degrees of Freedom.

As in the previous case, in the local coordinate system $Ox'/y'/z'$ (LCS), the direction of the Ox' coincides

with the bar axis

The constitutive equations of the bar system are written as $\{f\} = [D_{cm}]\{\varepsilon\}$,

Then

$$\{f\}^T = \{N \quad Q_y \quad Q_z \quad M_x \quad M_y \quad M_z\},$$

$$\{\varepsilon\}^T = \{\varepsilon_x \quad \chi'_y \quad \chi'_z \quad \chi \quad \chi_y \quad \chi_z\}.$$

Here $\varepsilon_x, \chi, \chi_y, \chi_z$ – axial strain, relative angle of twist, and curvature of the bar axis, $N, Q_y, Q_z, M_x, M_y,$

M_z – axial and shear forces, torsional moment, and bending moments, respectively.

The diagonal entries of matrix $[D_{cm}] = [b_{ij}]$, ($i, j = 1, 2, \dots, 6$), are given by: $b_{11} = EF, b_{22} = EJ_z, b_{33} = EJ_y,$
 $b_{44} = GJ_x, b_{55} = EJ_y, b_{66} = EJ_z$. All other elements of matrix DDD are zero. Under geometric nonlinearity,

axial strain (11), the relative twist angle, and the curvature of the bar axis are considered:

$$\chi = \frac{d\phi_x}{dx}, \chi_y = -\frac{d^2w}{dx^2}, \chi_z = -\frac{d^2v}{dx^2} \quad (18)$$

Assume the following interpolation functions:

$$u = a_1 + a_2x, v = a_3 + a_4x + a_2x^2 + a_6x^3, w = a_7 + a_8x + a_9x^2 + a_{10}x^3,$$

$$\phi_x = a_{11} + a_{12}x, \phi_y = a_8 + 2a_9x + 3a_{10}x^2, \phi_z = a_4 + 2a_5x + 3a_6x^2 \quad (19)$$

Express the coefficients a_1, \dots, a_{12} in terms of the nodal displacements

$\{\delta\}^T = \{u_i, v_i, w_i, \phi_{xi}, \phi_{yi}, \phi_{zi}, u_j, v_j, w_j, \phi_{xj}, \phi_{yj}, \phi_{zj}\}$ - nodal displacement vector,

$$u_i = u|_{x=0} = a_1, v_i = v|_{x=0} = a_3, w_i = w|_{x=0} = a_7, \phi_{xi} = \phi|_{x=0} = a_{11}, \phi_{yi} = \phi|_{x=0} = a_8,$$

$$\phi_{zi} = \phi|_{x=0} = a_4, u_j = u|_{x=l} = a_1 + a_2l, v_j = v|_{x=l} = a_3 + a_4l + a_5l^2 + a_6l^3,$$

$$w_j = w|_{x=l} = a_7 + a_8l + a_9l^2 + a_{10}l^3, \phi_{xj} = \phi|_{x=l} = a_{11} + a_{12}l, \phi_{yj} = \phi|_{x=l} = a_8 + 2a_9l + 3a_{10}l^2,$$

$$\phi_{zj} = \phi|_{x=l} = a_4 + 2a_5l + 3a_6l^2.$$

If we denote $\{a\} = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{12}\}^T$, then, in matrix form $\{\delta\} = [A]\{a\}$, where the nonzero entries of the matrix are

$$[A] = [a_{ij}], (i, j = 1, 2, \dots, 6), a_{1,1} = a_{2,3} = a_{3,7} = a_{4,11} = a_{5,8} = a_{6,4} = a_{7,1} = a_{8,3} = a_{9,7} = a_{10,11} = 1;$$

$$a_{11,8} = a_{12,4} = 1;$$

$$a_{7,2} = a_{8,4} = a_{9,8} = a_{10,12} = l; a_{8,5} = a_{9,9} = l^2; a_{8,6} = a_{9,10} = l^3; a_{11,9} = a_{12,5} = 2l;$$

$$a_{11,10} = a_{12,6} = 3l^2.$$

To determine $\{\delta\}$, it is necessary to evaluate $[A]^{-1}$, then $\{\delta\} = [A]^{-1}\{a\}$.

The displacements of an arbitrary point on the bar axis are determined by the following formulas:

$$u = \left(1 - \frac{x}{l}\right) u_i + \frac{x}{l} u_j;$$

$$v = \left[1 - 3\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2 + 2\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^3\right] v_i + \left[3\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^3\right] v_j + l \left[\frac{x}{l} - 2\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^3\right] \phi_{zi} +$$

$$+ l \left[\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^3 - \left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2\right] \phi_{zj};$$

$$w = \left[1 - 3\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2 + 2\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^3\right] w_i + \left[3\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2 - 2\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^3\right] w_j + l \left[\frac{x}{l} - 2\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^3\right] \phi_{yi} +$$

$$+ l \left[\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^3 - \left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2\right] \phi_{yj}$$

$$\phi_x = \left(1 - \frac{x}{l}\right) \phi_{xi} + \frac{x}{l} \phi_{xj}$$

$$\phi_y = \left[1 - 4\frac{x}{l} + 3\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2\right] \phi_{yi} + \left[3\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2 - 2\frac{x}{l}\right] \phi_{yj} + \frac{6}{l} \left[\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2 + \frac{x}{l}\right] w_i + \frac{6}{l} \left[\frac{x}{l} - \left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2\right] w_j;$$

$$\phi_z = \left[1 - 4\frac{x}{l} + 3\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2\right] \phi_{zi} + \left[3\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2 - 2\frac{x}{l}\right] \phi_{zj} + \frac{6}{l} \left[\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2 + \frac{x}{l}\right] v_i + \frac{6}{l} \left[\frac{x}{l} - \left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2\right] v_j \quad (20)$$

$$\text{Denote by } N_{1i} = 1 - \frac{x}{l}; N_{1j} = \frac{x}{l}; N_{2i} = 1 - 3\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2 + 2\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^3; N_{2j} = 3\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2 - 2\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^3;$$

$$N_{3i} = l \left[\frac{x}{l} - 2\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^3\right]; N_{3j} = l \left[\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^3 - \left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2\right] \quad (21)$$

$$N'_{2i} = \frac{6}{l} \left[\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2 - \frac{x}{l}\right]; N'_{2j} = \frac{6}{l} \left[\frac{x}{l} - \left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2\right]; N_{3i} = 1 - 4\frac{x}{l} + 3\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2; N_{3j} = 3\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^2 + 2\frac{x}{l}$$

Then, the shape function and differentiation matrices are, respectively, given by:

$$[N] = \begin{bmatrix} N_{1i} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & N_{1j} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & N_{2i} & 0 & 0 & 0 & N_{3i} & 0 & N_{2j} & 0 & 0 & 0 & N_{3j} \\ 0 & 0 & N_{2i} & 0 & N_{3i} & 0 & 0 & 0 & N_{2j} & 0 & N_{3j} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & N_{1i} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & N'_{1j} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & N'_{2i} & 0 & N'_{3i} & 0 & 0 & 0 & N'_{2j} & 0 & N'_{3j} & 0 \\ 0 & N'_{2i} & 0 & 0 & 0 & N'_{3i} & 0 & N'_{2j} & 0 & 0 & 0 & N'_{3j} \end{bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

$$[B_0] = \begin{bmatrix} N'_{1i} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & N'_{1j} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -N'''_{2i} & 0 & 0 & 0 & -N'''_{3i} & 0 & -N'''_{2j} & 0 & 0 & 0 & -N'''_{3j} \\ 0 & 0 & -N'''_{2i} & 0 & -N'''_{3i} & 0 & 0 & 0 & -N'''_{2j} & 0 & -N'''_{3j} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & N'_{1i} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & N'_{1j} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -N''_{2i} & 0 & -N''_{3i} & 0 & 0 & 0 & -N''_{2j} & 0 & -N''_{3j} & 0 \\ 0 & -N''_{2i} & 0 & 0 & 0 & -N''_{3i} & 0 & -N''_{2j} & 0 & 0 & 0 & -N''_{3j} \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

Where « $''$ » - where the prime denotes a derivative

The stiffness matrix $[K_0]$ is defined by the expression presented in [14]. In the nonlinear formulation, only axial strains are considered.

To consider the program for a six-degree-of-freedom bar as a special case of the program for determining the stress-strain state of a twelve-degree-of-freedom bar, the nodal displacement vector is modified as follows:

$$\{\delta\} = \{u_i, v_i, w_i, u_j, v_j, w_j, \phi_{xi}, \phi_{yi}, \phi_{zi}, \phi_{xj}, \phi_{yj}, \phi_{zj}\}^T.$$

Accordingly, the shape function matrix is also modified as follows:

$$[N] = \begin{bmatrix} N_{1i} & 0 & 0 & N_{1j} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & N_{2i} & 0 & 0 & N_{2j} & 0 & 0 & 0 & N_{3i} & 0 & 0 & N_{3j} \\ 0 & 0 & N_{2i} & 0 & 0 & N_{2j} & 0 & N_{3i} & 0 & 0 & N_{3j} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & N_{1j} & 0 & 0 & N'_{1j} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & N'_{2i} & 0 & 0 & N'_{2j} & 0 & N'_{3i} & 0 & 0 & N'_{3j} & 0 \\ 0 & N'_{2i} & 0 & 0 & N'_{2j} & 0 & 0 & 0 & N'_{3i} & 0 & 0 & N'_{3j} \end{bmatrix} \quad (24)$$

Accordingly, additional notation is introduced for the known matrices:

$$[D] = \begin{bmatrix} [D'] & 0 \\ 0 & [D''] \end{bmatrix}, \text{ where } [D'] \text{ will consist of a single element } [D'] = [EF],$$

$$[D''] = \begin{bmatrix} EJ_z & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & EJ_z & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & GJ & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & EJ_y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & EJ_z \end{bmatrix} \quad (25)$$

The strain-displacement matrix $\{\varepsilon\}$ can be written as $\{\varepsilon\} = \{\varepsilon_0\} + \{\varepsilon_L\}$ (26)

$$\{\varepsilon_0\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon'_0 \\ \varepsilon''_0 \end{Bmatrix}, \{\varepsilon_L\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon'_L \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}, \{\delta\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \delta' \\ \delta'' \end{Bmatrix}, \varepsilon'_0 = \frac{du}{dx}, \varepsilon'_L = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{du}{dx} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dv}{dx} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dx} \right)^2 \right]$$

Introduce the notation:

$$[B_0] = \begin{bmatrix} [B'_0] & 0 \\ [B''_0] & [B'''_0] \end{bmatrix}, [B_L] = \begin{bmatrix} [B'_L] & [B''_L] \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \{\theta\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{du}{dx} & \frac{dv}{dx} & \frac{dw}{dx} \end{Bmatrix}^T \quad (27)$$

$$\{\varepsilon'_0\} = \frac{1}{l} [-1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0] \begin{Bmatrix} u_i \\ u_j \\ v_i \\ v_j \\ w_i \\ w_j \end{Bmatrix} = [B'_0] \{\delta'\}, \text{ t.e. } [B'_0] = \frac{1}{l} [-1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0],$$

l – length of the finite element, $\{\delta'\}, \{\delta''\}$ - matrices of linear and angular displacements

Thus $\{\varepsilon'_L\} = \frac{1}{2} \{\theta\}^T [G] \{\delta\}$, where

$$[G] = \begin{bmatrix} N'_{1i} & 0 & 0 & N'_{1j} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & N'_{2i} & 0 & 0 & N'_{2j} & 0 & 0 & 0 & N'_{3i} & 0 & 0 & N'_{3j} \\ 0 & 0 & N'_{2i} & 0 & 0 & N'_{2j} & 0 & N'_{3i} & 0 & 0 & N'_{3j} & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$[G] = [G'] [G''],$$

$$[G'] = \begin{bmatrix} N'_{2i} & 0 & 0 & N'_{1j} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & N'_{2i} & 0 & 0 & N'_{2j} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & N'_{2i} & 0 & 0 & N'_{2j} \end{bmatrix}, [G''] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & N'_{3i} & 0 & 0 & N'_{3j} \\ 0 & N'_{3i} & 0 & 0 & N'_{3j} & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Thus: $[B'_L] = \{\theta\}^T [G']$, $[B''_L] = \{\theta\}^T [G'']$ (28)

The nonlinear stiffness matrix $[K_L]$ is determined by the following expression:

$$[K_L] = \int (B_0^T D B_L + B_L^T D B_0 + B_L^T D B_0) dV \quad (29)$$

Express $[K_L]$ in terms of the new notation. Consider the following transformations:

$$[B_0]^T = \begin{bmatrix} [B'_0]^T & [B''_0]{}^T \\ 0 & [B'''_0]{}^T \end{bmatrix}, [B_L]^T = \begin{bmatrix} [B'_L]^T & 0 \\ [B''_L]{}^T & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$[B_L]^T [D] [B_0] = \begin{bmatrix} [B'_L]^T & 0 \\ [B''_L]{}^T & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} [D'] & 0 \\ 0 & [D''] \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} [B'_0] & 0 \\ [B''_0] & [B'''_0] \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} [B'_L]^T [D'] [B'_0] & 0 \\ [B''_L]{}^T [D''] [B'_0] & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
[B_L]^T [D] [B_L] &= \begin{bmatrix} [B'_T]^T & 0 \\ [B'_{L'}]^T & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} [D'] & 0 \\ 0 & [D''] \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} [B'_0] & [B'_{L'}] \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \\
&= \begin{bmatrix} [B'_L]^T [D'] [B'_L] & [B'_L]^T [D'] [B'_{L'}] \\ [B'_{L'}]^T [D'] [B'_L] & [B'_{L'}]^T [D'] [B'_{L'}] \end{bmatrix} \\
[B_0]^T [D] [B_L] &= \begin{bmatrix} [B'_T]^T & [B'_{0''}]^T \\ 0 & [B'_{0''}]^T \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} [D'] & 0 \\ 0 & [D''] \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} [B'_L] & [B'_{L'}] \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \\
&= \begin{bmatrix} [B'_0]^T [D'] [B'_L] & [B'_0]^T [D'] [B'_{L'}] \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}
\end{aligned}$$

Thus:

$$[K_L] = EF \int \begin{bmatrix} [B'_0]^T [B'_L] + [B'_L]^T [B'_0] + [B'_L]^T [B'_L] & [B'_0]^T [B'_{L'}] + [B'_L]^T [B'_{L'}] \\ [B'_{L'}]^T [B'_0] + [B'_{L'}]^T [B'_L] & [B'_{L'}]^T [B'_{L'}] \end{bmatrix} dx \quad (30)$$

The initial stress matrix is determined from Eq. (5):

$$\begin{aligned}
\int d[B_L]^T \{\sigma\} dV &= \int \begin{bmatrix} d[B'_L]^T & 0 \\ d[B'_{L'}]^T & 0 \end{bmatrix} \{\sigma\} dV = \int \begin{bmatrix} d[\theta^T G']^T & 0 \\ d[\theta^T G''] & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma' \\ \sigma'' \end{Bmatrix} dV = \\
&= \begin{bmatrix} [G']^T d\{\theta\} & 0 \\ [G'']^T d\{\theta\} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma' \\ \sigma'' \end{Bmatrix} dV \\
\text{Since } [G']^T d\{\theta\} \{\sigma'\} &= [G']^T \begin{Bmatrix} d\left(\frac{du}{dx}\right) \\ d\left(\frac{dv}{dx}\right) \\ d\left(\frac{dw}{dx}\right) \end{Bmatrix} [N_x] = N_x [[G']^T [G'] \quad [G'] [G'']] d\{\delta\},
\end{aligned}$$

the initial stress matrix takes the following final form:

$$[K_\sigma] = \int_0^l N_x \begin{bmatrix} [G']^T [G'] & [G']^T [G''] \\ [G'']^T [G'] & [G'']^T [G''] \end{bmatrix} dx \quad (31)$$

Analysis of Results and Examples

To investigate the accuracy and convergence of the solution, several benchmark problems were analyzed. As the first benchmark problem, an inclined elastic bar element is considered to illustrate the influence of axial effects (Figure 1). Although this problem is very simple, it was selected because of the small amount of required computation and because it makes it possible to reveal the expected behavior of solutions for more complex problems. This problem has been studied by a number of researchers [12,15]; therefore, the accuracy of the obtained results can be assessed through comparative analysis. In the performed calculations, the bar is subjected only to compression. The problem is essentially nonlinear and involves large displacements.

Figure 1-Diagram of an inclined rod element

The calculations were performed using the following input data:

$EF=10$ kg compressive stiffness.

$h=1$ cm — projection of the bar length onto the Oy axis

$l=100$ cm — projection of the bar length onto the Ox axis

$k=6$ kg/cm — spring stiffness coefficient

The bar is modeled as a single bar finite element with four degrees of freedom (transverse deflection and axial displacement at each of the two nodes). Since the bar is not subjected to bending and a concentrated vertical force is applied at the node, the displacements are approximated using formulas (20):

$$u = \left(1 - \frac{x}{l}\right) u_i + \frac{x}{l} u_j, v = \left(1 - \frac{x}{l}\right) v_i + \frac{x}{l} v_j \tag{32}$$

In matrix form:

$$\{U\} = [N]\{\delta\}, \text{ where } \{U\} = \{u \ v\}^T, [N] = \begin{bmatrix} N_{1i} & 0 & N_{1j} & 0 \\ 0 & N_{1i} & 0 & N_{1j} \end{bmatrix} - \text{shape functions, where}$$

$\{\delta\} = \{u_1 \ v_1 \ u_2 \ v_2\}^T$ - nodal displacement vector.

The axial strain is given by:

$$\epsilon_x = \frac{du}{dx} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{dv}{dx}\right)^2 \tag{33}$$

The main matrices can be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \{\epsilon_x\} &= [N'_{1i} \ 0 \ N'_{1j} \ 0]\{\delta\} = [B_0]\{\delta\}, \\ \{\theta\} &= [0 \ N'_{1i} \ 0 \ N'_{1j}]\{\delta\} = [G]\{\delta\}, \\ \{\epsilon_x\} &= \frac{1}{2}\{\theta\}^T\{\theta\} = \frac{1}{2}\{\delta\}^T[G]^T[G]\{\delta\} = \frac{1}{2}[B_L]\{\delta\}, \\ [B_0] &= [N'_{1i} \ 0 \ N'_{1j} \ 0], [B_L] = \{\delta\}^T[G]^T[G] \end{aligned} \tag{34}$$

In this formulation, the constitutive matrix $[D]$ is given by: $[D] = [EF]$.

As can be seen from Fig. 1, the local coordinate system (LCS) does not coincide with the global coordinate system (GCS) and is rotated by an angle α .

The transformation matrix from the LCS to the GCS is given by:

$$[L] = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \alpha & \sin \alpha \\ -\sin \alpha & \cos \alpha \end{bmatrix}, \text{ где } \cos \alpha = \frac{l}{\sqrt{l^2+h^2}}, \sin \alpha = \frac{h}{\sqrt{l^2+h^2}} \tag{35}$$

Boundary conditions: $u_1 = 0, v_1 = 0, u_2 = 0$ (36)

A comparative analysis of the problem solution obtained by different methods for various load levels ($P=9P=9P=9$ kg, $P=12P=12P=12$ kg, $P=24P=24P=24$ kg) is presented in Table 1 and agrees with the numerical solutions reported in [12,15].

Table 1

Comparative characteristics of solving the problem by various methods

Load, P (kg)	Displacement, cm			
	According to the works [1, 18]		of this work	
	Linear	Nonlinear	Linear	Nonlinear
9	-0,56	-1,76	-0,56	-1,48
12,0	-0,75	-2,00	-0,75	-2,08
24,0	-1,50	-2,48	-1,50	-2,88

As the second benchmark problem, an elastic cantilever beam subjected to a bending moment at the free end is considered. This problem involves purely bending effects and is examined in [16]. Its simplicity makes it possible to obtain simple analytical formulas describing geometrically nonlinear effects (Figure 2).

Figure 2-Calculation element diagram

The maximum deflection and axial displacement occur at the free end of the beam and are given by:

$$u = l - \rho \sin \phi, v = \rho(1 - \cos \phi) \tag{37}$$

u, v - are the horizontal and vertical displacements of the beam, respectively.

l — beam length, ρ - beam curvature, ϕ - rotation angle of the free end.

For the numerical example, a beam with the following parameters is considered:

$M=10^5 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{cm}$ applied static load moment,

$F=10 \text{ cm}^2$ -cross-sectional area of the beam,

$E=2 \cdot 10^6$ - modulus of elasticity.

Since the neutral axis is not stretched under pure bending, $\phi = \frac{l}{\rho} = \frac{Ml}{EI} = 1$ rad, where

$$l = \rho.$$

Substituting the obtained value of ϕ, ρ, l into Eq. (37) yields

$$u=100(1-\sin 1)=15,83 \text{ cm}, v=100(1-\cos 1)=45,97 \text{ cm}.$$

In the finite element formulation, the beam is modeled as a single finite element with eight degrees of freedom (transverse deflection, axial displacement, and two rotational degrees of freedom at each of the two nodes). Considering that the problem is treated in a plane formulation, the displacements of an arbitrary point on the bar axis are expressed as:

$$u = N_{2i}u_1 + N_{3i}\phi_{x1} + N_{2i}u_2 + N_{3j}\phi_{x2}, v = N_{2i}v_1 + N_{3i}\phi_{y1} + N_{2i}v_2 + N_{3j}\phi_{y2} \quad (38)$$

In matrix form

$$\{U\} = \begin{Bmatrix} u \\ v \end{Bmatrix}, [N] = \begin{bmatrix} N_{2i} & N_{3i} & 0 & 0 & N_{2j} & N_{3j} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & N_{2i} & N_{3i} & 0 & 0 & N_{2j} & N_{3j} \end{bmatrix} \text{ - shape function}$$

$\{\delta\} = \{u_1, \phi_{x1}, v_1, \phi_{y1}, u_2, \phi_{x2}, v_2, \phi_{y2}\}$ - nodal displacement vector.

The axial strain from (11) $\varepsilon_x = \frac{du}{dx} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{du}{dx} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dv}{dx} \right)^2 \right]$, beam curvature $\rho = \frac{d^2v}{dx^2}$.

The stress $\{N, M\}^T$ and strain $\{\varepsilon_x, \rho\}^T$ vectors are related through the constitutive matrix $[D] = \begin{bmatrix} EF & 0 \\ 0 & EJ \end{bmatrix}$

Thus, matrix $[B]$ is given by:

$$[B] = \begin{bmatrix} N'_{2i} & N'_{3i} & 0 & 0 & N'_{2j} & N'_{3j} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & N''_{2i} & N''_{3i} & 0 & 0 & N''_{2j} & N''_{3j} \end{bmatrix} \quad (39)$$

Where « $''$ » - the prime denotes differentiation

The nonlinear strain matrix takes the following form:

$$\{\varepsilon_L\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon'_L \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}, \text{ где } \varepsilon'_L = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{du}{dx} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dv}{dx} \right)^2 \right] \quad (40)$$

This relation can be represented using the following notation and transformations:

$$\{\theta\}^T = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{du}{dx} & \frac{dv}{dx} \end{bmatrix}, \quad [B] = \begin{bmatrix} N'_{2i} & N'_{3i} & 0 & 0 & N'_{2j} & N'_{3j} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & N''_{2i} & N''_{3i} & 0 & 0 & N''_{2j} & N''_{3j} \end{bmatrix} \{\delta\} = [G]\{\delta\} \quad (41)$$

$$\{\varepsilon'_L\} = \frac{1}{2} \{\theta\}^T \{\theta\} = \frac{1}{2} [[G]\{\delta\}]^T [G]\{\delta\} = \frac{1}{2} \{\delta\}^T [G] \{\delta\} = \frac{1}{2} [B'_L] \{\delta\}, [B'_L] = \{\delta\}^T [G]^T [G]$$

The nonlinear differentiation matrix $[B_L]$ is given by:

$$[B_L] = \begin{bmatrix} B'_L \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (42)$$

The initial stress matrix is determined according to Eq. (31). The boundary conditions for the clamped end are specified as $u_1 = 0, v_1 = 0, w_1 = 0$.

The free-end displacements are close to the analytically obtained results, which confirms the high accuracy of the developed program.

Comparative characteristics of moving the free end of the beam by various methods

Results of the solution	u_2 (cm)	v_2 (cm)
By [1]	-15,853	45,970
By [15]	-15,850	45,197
According to the algorithm of this work	-15,610	45,770

The obtained numerical results allow the conclusion that the proposed algorithm can be applied to the analysis of geometrically nonlinear bar systems subjected to static loading.

Conclusion

Based on the finite element method, the governing equations for solving the static elastic problem of a spatial bar system considering geometric nonlinearity have been obtained. The principal relationships, solution method, and computational scheme have been established. An algorithm for solving the problem and high-level computer programs have been developed and verified on benchmark problems [17,18].

The proposed algorithm was used for the calculation and analysis of the elastic behavior of a specific platform. Analysis of the influence of large displacements on the elastic nodal displacements of the platform showed that accounting for geometric nonlinearity significantly alters the results obtained for a linear bar system; the computed displacements are 1.5–2.2 times greater than the corresponding displacements obtained from linear analysis.

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